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INFORMATION AND EDUCATION IN THE AGE OF TECHNOLOGICAL CONVERGENCE

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Abstract

India in the post WTO (2005) era despite a great deal of Planning Paralysis at the Centre has emerged as a global power. Sadri and Jayashree have elsewhere argued that in such an era the business environment is marked by concurrent collapse of structures and functions on the one hand and organizational change which is non-linear and non-Newtonian on the other. Technological convergence is a logical symptom of objective social reality under such circumstances and this paper has been written against this backdrop.

Key words: *Convergence, Educational environments, Management sciences, School broadcasting, General educational programming, Information technology*

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INTRODUCTION

The computer is the ‘teaching-machine’ corresponding to the fifth generation of education (i.e. e-Learning). Its essence is its universality, and its power to simulate. Because it can take on a thousand forms and can serve a thousand functions (through respective software), it can appeal to a thousand tastes. This enables the proliferation of digital technology in the education environment due to the interests shown by the parents, students, governing authorities, and educators.

But there is mysticism involved about the practical applications of computers in education environment. Sometimes the tsunami of advancements in technology hijacks the issues corresponding to their implementation in education domain. Also the practical advantages of Information Technology in education get unnoticed in the midst of technological details.

This paper discusses the fifth generation of education characterized by the introduction of Information Technology in education process. It also discusses the factors responsible for the increasing adoption of e-Learning and provides advantages behind them in concrete terms.

Basics: According to the Wikipedia *Technological convergence* is defined as the tendency for different technological systems to evolve toward performing similar tasks. [Digital convergence](#) can refer to previously separate technologies such as voice (and telephony features), data (and productivity applications), and video that now share resources and interact with each other synergistically. *Telecommunications convergence, network convergence* or simply *convergence* are therefore broad terms, in the era of concurrent collapse and non Newtonian change, that are used to describe emerging [telecommunications](#) technologies, and [network architecture](#) used to migrate multiple communications services into a single network. Specifically this involves the converging of previously distinct media such as [telephony](#) and [data communications](#) into common interfaces on single devices.

The rise of digital communication in the late 20th century has made it possible for media organizations (or individuals) to deliver text, audio, and video material over the same wired, wireless, or fiber-optic connections. At the same time, it inspired some media organizations to explore multimedia delivery of information. This digital convergence of

news media, in particular, was called *Mediamorphosis* by researcher Roger Fidler, in his 1997 book by that name. Today, we are surrounded by a multi-level convergent media world where all modes of communication and information are continually reforming to adapt to the enduring demands of technologies, "changing the way we create, consume, learn and interact with each other"

Convergence in this instance is defined as the interlinking of computing and other information technologies, media content, and communication networks that has arisen as the result of the evolution and popularization of the Internet as well as the activities, products and services that have emerged in the digital media space. Many experts view this as simply being the tip of the iceberg, as all facets of institutional activity and social life such as business, government, art, journalism, health, and education are increasingly being carried out in these digital media spaces across a growing network of [information and communication technology](#) devices.

In view of the importance of this symbiotic development IT and Education sectors have been brought closer to each other than ever before. This paper attempts to shed some

light on this new convergence of knowledge and technology from a management science perspective.

Generations of education environments:

The Indian culture has a rich educational tradition. The origin and growth of Indian Education System progressed through five generations – namely;

- Pre-Vedic system of education: oral experience sharing (1500 BC – 1000 BC)
- Post-Vedic system of education: formal education system (Gurukul system)

(1000 BC – 200 BC)

- Buddhist system of education: mass education through educational institutions

(e.g. Takshashila, Nalanda) (200 BC – 1000 AD)

- Islamic system of education: education proliferation through books (1000 AD – 1600 AD)
- System Overlap when various kingdoms had their own unique education features (1600-1800)

- British system of education: Western education system post Lord Maclay's intervention (1800 AD onwards)
- System catharsis when India's education system tried various experiments and is now somewhat stable (1950-2010).

While it is an important area for consideration, it will be seen that the western education system overlaps on traditional Indian education system. Also the western education system has global presence. Hence, this research is oriented towards western education environments.

The origin and growth of western education system has also progressed through five distinct generations. Prior to writing, books and schools, learning was essentially experiential (the first generation of learning). The individual learned by doing. The cave paintings and hieroglyphics of the ancients were to instruct future generations about what had been learnt by their ancestors.

The formal education process was developed in the 5th century B.C. in Athens with the advent of the Socratic-method based on deduction. Until that time learning was very much a process of everyday

experience. The idea of learning in an abstract setting (rather than experience) constitutes the first formal education process (the second generation of education) that eventually gave rise to today's educational system.

The learning process tilted even more towards formal education in the third generation, with the academies founded by Aristotle and Plato in 4th century B.C. These early academies for many years relied on the oral tradition of the teacher reciting from memory, while students memorized the recitation. Faculty and students then engaged in a dialogue to discover the truth. The origination of symbol systems eventually led to the formal writing of codified knowledge in documents known as books. The first books were extremely rare, and writers were severely criticized for introducing them into the education system. In this early period, books were the exclusive domain of faculty. Instead of reciting lectures from memory, faculty read to students from handcrafted manuscripts. For reasons of economics and ideology, students didn't have access to such books. This era formed the latter part of third generation.

The invention of the printing press erased the economic argument against students’ having access to books. The wide availability of books eventually ushered in the fourth generation of learning, which has persisted until this time. The advent of the book and the printing press added a major level of productivity enhancement towards the proliferation of education.

The emergence of digital technology started the fifth generation. Its multidimensional approach is changing our traditional perceptions towards management of education environment, transfer of instructional resources and teaching-learning process itself.

These five generations of education can be summarized as;

- first generation: experience sharing (through auditory, cave paintings, and hieroglyphics)
- second generation: formal education, 5th century B.C.
- third generation: formal institutions of higher education, 4th century B.C.
- fourth generation: printing press enabled students’ access to the books, 15th century

- fifth generation: digital technology enhanced the educational environment, 20th century

Computers are used in education environment following different approaches; to manage education institutions, to provide virtual learning environments (VLE), and to provide instructional resources.

The first is the extension of the current procedures. It represents the same activities using a new tool (through adaptation of digital technology to suit present setup). The second and third approach introduces a catalyst in the form of a computer, in educational environment. It proposes the use of computers in teaching-learning process to assist teacher and learner. It is also proven that they together enhance the teaching-learning process.

Fifth generation of education environment: Fifth generation education environment is tightly bound to the advent of digital technology and its advancement throughout the 20th century into 21st century. Table 1 (given at the end of the paper) provides a brief trace-out of its origin and progress.

Digital technology in education

environment: The computer is the ‘teaching-machine’ of fifth generation ^[5]. Its essence is its universality, and its power to simulate. Because it can take on a thousand forms and can serve a thousand functions (through respective software), it can appeal to a thousand tastes. This enables the proliferation of digital technology in education environment due to the interests shown by the parents, students, governing authorities, and educators.

The parents themselves are demanding computers in educational institutions. Middle class parents in particular seem to feel that their children are receiving an inferior education unless computers are available. This reflects the fact that society sees computers as magical devices, ones people hope will solve the major social problems. Parents also see computer skills as valuable for future jobs. Information and communication technologies (ICTs)—which include radio and television, as well as newer digital technologies such as computers and the Internet—have been touted as potentially powerful enabling tools for educational change and reform.

The Students generally show high enthusiasm about working with computers

which improves their academic motivation. Also, students project feelings, intentions, and psychology onto the computer which supplements this.

E-learning encompasses learning at all levels, both formal and non-formal, that uses an information network—the Internet, an intranet (LAN) or extranet (WAN)—whether wholly or in part, for course delivery, interaction and/or facilitation. Others prefer the term *online learning*. *Web-based learning* is a subset of E-learning and refers to learning using an Internet browser (such as Netscape or Internet Explorer).

The governing authorities are supporting and sometimes sponsoring the use of digital technology in education at multiple levels. In India, ‘country classroom’ project initiated by University Grants Commission (UGC), the Satellite Instructional Television Experiment (SITE), government’s initiative to interlink all technical education institutes with the Anna University of Technology in Chennai, UGC’s INFLIBNET which was setup to connect university libraries throughout India, UGC’s proposal to link 5000 colleges in the country through an information network system to ensure uniformity in access to teaching material, Indian Space Research Organization’s

(ISRO) EDUSAT satellite to take the teaching expertise of expert educators to remote areas and Computer Literacy at Secondary School (CLASS) project are instances of such trend.

India’s 10th Five Year Plan (2002-07) states, ‘8.52: During the Tenth Plan it is proposed to provide computer connectivity to 140 government senior secondary schools through *Vidya Vahini* Programme and upgrade the IT infrastructure at Delhi University through *Gyan Vahini* Programme. Later, efforts would be made to replicate these programmes in other schools and colleges by involving private sector’. This underlines the positive approach of governing authorities towards this paradigm.

Radio and television have been used widely as educational tools since the 1920s and the 1950s, respectively. There are three general approaches to the use of radio and TV broadcasting in education.

- **direct class teaching**, where broadcast programming substitutes for teachers on a temporary basis;
- **school broadcasting**, where broadcast programming provides complementary teaching and

learning resources not otherwise available; and

- **General educational programming over community**, national and international stations which provide general and informal educational opportunities.

Universities whose motto is to have *excellence in the classroom* are bound to develop. Educators there are encouraging the use of computers in education following their proven advantages in education setup. Teachers are not only interested in use of computers in education but they also have positive feelings toward them. In the right hands computers become an important tool for research. In the right conditions this research is converted into classroom teaching. Not all are comfortable with this. For instance professors who cannot confidently teach at the postgraduate level are known to opt for developing and administering equally important vocational training and general knowledge programs so that an overall win-win situation emerges.

It is proven that use of computers as teaching-machine is at least as effective as traditional instruction and may actually lead

to significant improvements in some subject areas. It is found that when computers are used the students learn instructional materials at a faster rate – in some cases up to 40 percent faster. In particular, when used to present certain kinds of material graphically rather than textually, the computer can help a majority of learners comprehend some aspects of that material faster and more accurately. Thus computer-based instruction results in significant reductions of instructional time.

One hour per day with a computer can theoretically provide a student with more interaction than he or she would receive in a day in a regular classroom. It also produces favorable attitudes towards computers by students.

It is also discussed that to cope up with the accelerating change computer is necessary in education system. Thus making it the fourth aspect of education (along with reading, writing, and arithmetic)

Researchers have conducted a number of meta-analyses (analyses of the previous research studies) to determine the impact of digital technology on student achievement (Table 2 given at the end of the paper). These meta-analyses were conducted independently by different researchers,

focused on the different uses of computers and multimedia technologies with different populations, and differed in terms of the methodology used to identify studies and analyze results. Nevertheless each meta-analysis concluded that instructional programs that included technology show a positive impact on student achievement.

Advantages of Information Technology in Education: Following this discussion, the discussed advantages of computers in education can be summarized as;

1. **Learners enjoy using computers:** The computer has very high motivational value. People of all ages hear about computers constantly through news-papers, television, and films. Although the computer is not always pictured favorably, for most learners, particularly most young ones, it is presented as an exciting new device. So students are prepared for computers, even eager to have contact with them.
2. **Individualization:** Most learning-theorists agree with

comment that learning is a very individualized process. Students have quite different backgrounds and abilities, and they probably differ, from the standpoint of learning, in many ways unknown at present. The time required for learning may also differ from student to student. A central problem in any educational system is how to reach the individual student effectively. This problem is seldom addressed adequately in current educational systems. With good material available, computers can allow individualization responsive to student needs.

3. **Faster learning:** Results suggest that curriculum based on computer-based learning can cut 30 percent from the time students need to learn something. The major advantage comes from individualization. That is, students do not have to spend much time on a subject they know when using good computer-based learning modules.

4. **Visualization:** Graphics are very extremely important in the learning process, as suggested by the brain research and by common educational practices. Hence the fact that computers today can provide a remarkable range of pictorial capabilities is important for learning.
5. **Interaction:** Most learning psychologists would agree upon another factor with respect to learning: Active learning works better than passive learning. One of the computer’s main advantages in education is its capability to provide an interactive learning experience.
6. **Communications:** Interaction with other students – peer interaction – is very valuable in the learning process; computers can serve well in encouraging peer learning in a variety of ways.

Conclusion: Convergence is an inevitable reality today and management scientists should be well schooled to take account of this. The onus for its success lies on (a) the professor who should be knowledgeable

enough to impart learning, (b) the student who must be enthused enough to accept the wisdom and, (c) the university to create the environment to facilitate this. Thus it is clear that the fifth generation of education is here to stay. It provides concrete reasons for its adoption and proliferation. The involved entities, i.e. teachers, students, management, and parents, are counting on the phenomenon of e-Learning with expectations. The inquiry conducted in this domain also supports them. The benefits of e-Learning can be realized through more entertaining form of education, individual attention towards the students, self-paced learning, decreased complexity through improved visualization aids, active involvement of the students in the learning process, and improved interaction among the peers.

References:

1. *'India's Five Year Plans: Complete Documents'*, Academic Foundation, 2003
2. *'Informational Technology and It's Impact on American Education'*, Office of Technology Assessment, U. S. Congress, 1982, p 128-133
3. Atieh, S., *'How to Get A College Degree Via The Internet'*, Magna Books, 2004
4. Blackman, Colin. *Convergence between Telecommunications and Other Media: How Should Regulation Adapt?.* *Telecommunication Policy*, Vol. 22, No.3 1998. Great Britain. Print
5. Bork., A., *'Personal Computers for Education'*, Harper and Row Publishers, 1985
6. Brown, J. S., *'Uses of Artificial Intelligence and Advanced Computer Technology in Education'*, Academic Press Inc., 1977
7. Fischer, G., *'Where CAI Is Effective: A Survey of The Research'*, *Electronic Learning*, November-December 1983
8. Gleason, G. T., *'Microcomputers in Education: The State of The Art'*, *Educational Technology*, March 1981

9. Hofmeister, A. M., 'Microcomputers in Perspective', Exceptional Children, October 1983
10. Homes, G., 'Computer-Assisted Instruction: A Discussion of Some of The Issues for would-be Implementers', Education Technology, September 1982
11. Ingersoll, G. M., Smith, C. B., and Elliot, P., 'Microcomputers in American Public Schools: A National Survey', *Educational Computer*, October 1983
12. Jayashree S, Sadri S and Nayak N (2009): *Strategic Human Resources Management*, Jaico Pub Co. Delhi
13. Jayashree S, *Fundamental Issues in People Management*, Bharati Publications, Delhi 2014
14. Jenkins, Henry, *Convergence Culture*, New York University Press, New York, 2006
15. Kemeny, J. C., and Kurtz, T., 'Dartmouth Time Sharing', *Science*, October 1968
16. Levien, R. E., 'The Emerging Technology: Instructional Uses of The Computer in Higher Education', McGraw-Hill, 1972
17. Menon, Siddhartha. "Policy Initiative Dilemmas On Media Convergence: A Cross National Perspective." Conference Papers -- International Communication Association (2006) *Communication & Mass Media Complete*. Web. 20 Nov. 2011
18. Merton, A., 'Computers in The Classroom', *Technology in The Classroom*, September 1983
19. Molnar, A. R., 'Viable Goals for New Educational Technology Efforts: Science Education and The New Technological Revolution', Educational Technology, September 1975
20. Negroponte, Nicholas. *Being Digital*. Knopf, New York, 1995.
21. Oliver, R. W., 'e-Learning: Fifth Generation Learning and It's Impact on Management Education', in 'E-Service: New Directions in Theory and Practice', Roland, R., and Kannan, P. K. (eds.), Sharpe, 2002

22. Orlansky, J., 'Effectiveness of CAI: A Different Finding', *Electronics Learning*, September 1983
23. Papert, S., 'Mindstorms: *Children, Computers and Powerful Ideas*', Basic Books, 1980
24. Papert, S., '*The Children's Machine: Rethinking School in The Age of The Computer*', Basic Books, 1993
25. Pressey, S. L., 'A Simple Apparatus Which Gives Tests and Scores – and Teaches', *School and Society*, May 1927
26. Raghavan, S. S., '*Microcomputers in School Education*', Prentice-Hall of India, 1990 p 4
27. Ramaiah, Y. R. '*Distance Education and Open Learning*', Mittal Publications, 2001, p 153-187
28. Ramchandran, P., and Ramkumar, V., '*Education in India*', National Book Trust, 2005, p 1-104
29. Roblyer, J. D., 'Measuring The Impact of Computers in Instruction: A Non-Technical Review of Research for Educators', *AEDS*, 1985
30. Sadri S and Jayashree S, *Business Ethics and Corporate Governance*, 1st Edition, Current Books, Agra 2011
31. Sadri S and Jayashree S, *Human Resources Management in Modern India: concepts and cases*, Himalaya Publications, Mumbai 2012
32. Sadri S and Makkar U (eds), *Future Directions in Management*, Bharati Publications, Delhi 2012
33. Sadri S, *Excellence in Management*, Lap Lambert Publications, Germany 2014
34. Smith, P. R., '*CAL-85: A Symposium in Advances in Computer Assisted Learning*', Pergamon Press, 1986
35. Spencer, M., and Baskin, L., '*Computers in The Classroom*', *Childhood Education*, March-April 1983
36. Taylor, R. P., and Cunniff, N., '*Moving Computing and Education Beyond Rhetoric*', *College Record*, 1988
37. Taylor, R. T., '*The Computer in The School: Tutor, Tool, Tutee*',

- Teachers College Press, 1980, p 213-260
38. Turkle, S., *'The Second Self: Computers and The Human Spirit'*, Simon and Schuster, 1984
39. Valdez, G., *'Computer-based Technology and Learning: Evolving Uses and Expectations'*, North Central Regional Educational Lab, 2000
40. Van Dijk, J. *The Network Society*,